

Australian National PID Action Plan 2026

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2026 at a Glance

Introduction

The [Australian National Persistent Identifier \(PID\) Strategy 2024](#) aspires to accelerate Australian research quality, efficiency and impact through universal use of persistent identifiers. Its primary goals are to improve research quality and efficiency and to optimise the national research and innovation ecosystem. By connecting information on a national scale, the strategy enables Australia to harness the power of data to drive innovation, in crucial areas such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), and prepares Australia for the changing landscape of research integrity and reproducibility in the age of AI.

The Strategy is being implemented through an accompanying Roadmap of which this annual National PID Action Plan is part, together with a set of accompanying tools for achieving the Strategy’s intent. The ARDC and AAF provide foundational PID services in partnership with international PID providers and jointly support the National PID Strategic Advisory Group (NPSAG). NPSAG members reviewed, contributed to, and approved this Action Plan. NPSAG will continue to provide input and track progress throughout the year.

This Action Plan outlines a set of collective, collaborative, national-scale actions that advance the Strategy’s intent in 2026. There is strong organisational support behind this intent, evidenced in 2025 engagements including release of ARC and NHMRC PID Action Plans, 28 universities represented in the institutional stakeholder action group, 12 NCRIS facilities in the NCRIS group. This Plan seeks to build on the 2025 achievements and support the National PID Strategy by describing the key collaborative national actions required in 2026 to create shared value for all stakeholders. It does so by ensuring:

1. Strategic alignment: actions are aligned with the national research and innovation strategy, and with international PID developments.
2. National capacity and capability uplift: there is a strong focus on developing national capability and uplift including operational and technical capacity that can bring productivity improvements and reduction in red tape across the sector.
3. Underpinning service delivery: national PID services and infrastructure to support realisation of the Strategy, capable of evolving to meet sector needs as they arise.

1. Strategic alignment

1.1 Strategic Governance

Goal	To facilitate shared national action, to create shared value for all stakeholders and to position the National PID Strategy within the Australian research policy, capability and funding environment.
Lead(s)	National PID Strategic Advisory Group (NPSAG), supported by the ARDC & AAF joint secretariat. NPSAG includes representatives of ARC, NHMRC, ARMS, CAUL, CAUDIT, NCRIS, Department of Education, AAF, ARDC and leading

	independent experts with an academic research background.
Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide oversight of, and input into, the National PID Strategy and its implementation including the National PID Action Plan 2026 ● Monitor progress against the Strategy through annual review of the National PID Benchmarking (see Action 1.3) ● Advocate for the Strategy through strategic conversations with senior stakeholders and target groups, such as system vendors ● Ensure alignment with ARDC’s Research Data Commons projects to realise PID integration in specific domains ● Monitor and where appropriate, influence national strategy, funding and policy briefs
Inputs	NPSAG meetings
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strategic guidance and monitoring of the National PID Action Plan ● Submissions into relevant national policy briefs ● Strategic messaging for key stakeholder groups

1.2 International Alignment

Goal	To ensure that the National PID Strategy is aligned internationally with other National PID Strategies and PID related policies such as Open Science and FAIR policies, and best practice. To contribute into international fora and bring learnings and cutting-edge developments into the Australian national PID strategy. Play a leadership role internationally in PIDs, share progress and learnings with the global community.
Lead(s)	ARDC, AAF
Method	<p>Participate in international bodies and activities that advance the Australian National PID Strategy and Roadmap</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research Data Alliance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ National PID Strategies ○ PIDs for Instruments (PIDINST) ● PID Providers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Executive Board representation - ORCID, DataCite, DOI Foundation ○ Working Groups and Committees - ROR Curation Board; DataCite Metadata WG; DataCite Community Engagement

	<p>Steering Group; Crossref Funders Group, ORCID Consortia Leads Interest Group</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ IGSN eV membership ● PID Initiatives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ PIDfest
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● International research community practices and policy including via discipline specific bodies ● International agreements on best practice and shared goals, in particular National PID Strategies ● Research on cross national data management and PID ecosystems ● Shared infrastructure agreements ● International PID service provider membership
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● National Strategy both informed by and aligned with, international best practice ● Agreed standards and messaging ● National PID services aligned with international standards and best practice ● Infrastructure planning

1.3 Annual National Benchmarking

Goal	Undertake National PID Benchmarking on an annual basis to monitor the Strategy and Roadmap’s impact and effectiveness over time
Lead(s)	ARDC
Method	Execute the code provided by Digital Science in the National PID Benchmarking Report on an annual basis and share results with NPSAG and the sector
Inputs	Digital Science National PID Benchmarking Report
Outputs	<p>Annual PID Benchmarking figures Communication of the Benchmarking to stakeholders and the broader research and government sector:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pulling out the key messages ● Telling a story (e.g. the funders story) ● Reflecting case studies

2. National capacity and capability uplift

2.1 Stakeholder engagement and support

2.1.1 Institutional engagement and support

Goal	This activity supports the National PID Strategy by ensuring universities and research institutions can inform, contribute to, and be supported in, realising the aspirations of the Strategy
Lead(s)	ARDC
Method	Institutional Stakeholder Action Group
Inputs	Existing co-designed toolkit, including Value Proposition Scenarios, Capability Maturity Model, Implementation Recipes and incorporated recommendations.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Focused use-cases and case studies representing the variety of institutions ● Toolkit review, potentially including Capability Maturity Model and Implementation Recipes gap analysis. ● PID Ready Platforms - Vendor & Publisher Strategy (co-developed across 2026 action areas)

2.1.2 Funder engagement and support

Goal	This engagement activity is designed to assist research funding agencies in realising their PID goals and aspirations, aligned with the intent of the National Strategy
Lead(s)	ARDC
Method	Funders Stakeholder Action Group
Inputs	Funder PID Action Plans and related policies
Outputs	Funder PID Action Plans Greater use of PIDs in funder systems, policies etc.

2.1.3 NCRIS facilities engagement and support

Goal	This activity supports the National PID Strategy by ensuring NCRIS facilities can inform, contribute to, and be supported in, realising the aspirations of the Strategy
Lead(s)	ARDC
Method	NCRIS Wide PID Uplift Group PIDs for Instruments (i4iOz) Community of Practice Cross NCRIS Microscopy Focus Group
Inputs	NCRIS expertise International best practice Alignment with RIC project Discipline specific international PID use guidelines
Outputs	Individual NCRIS facility PID action plans NCRIS wide PID action plan NCRIS Specific Best Practice Guides NCRIS PID infrastructure uplift

2.1.4 Journey mapping

Goal	This cross-stakeholder activity supports the National PID Strategy by mapping PID-related journeys
Lead(s)	ARDC
Method	Journey Mapping Working Group
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Prioritised focus areas and PIDs from the Institutions Value Proposition Scenarios, Capability Maturity Model, Implementation Recipes ● Funder PID Action Plans ● NCRIS Wide PID Uplift Group and i4iOz input ● Digital Science National PID Benchmarking Report recommendations
Outputs	Priority Journey Maps of current and uplifted states, informing action plans (end-to-end systemic plans, collaboratively developed, that cut across Stakeholders and Priority PIDs). Examples: Instruments from procurement to impact, including funding, data generation, output, reporting. Funding from pre-award to impact, including research activity, collaboration, outputs.

2.2 Priority PIDs

2.2.1 PIDs for research grants and agencies

Goal	Increase the discoverability, transparency and linking of grants to funding agencies, researchers, and research outputs
Lead(s)	ARDC
Method	Funders Stakeholder Action Group ARDC DataCite DOI Consortium PID Ready Platforms -Vendor Strategy

2.2.2 PIDs for Instruments and Facilities

Goal	To adopt agreed national guidelines on the adoption of PIDs for instruments as a precursor to greater instrument findability and improved provenance. To identify facilities with a PID so that they can be linked to the instruments they own. To support the visibility of research instruments, facilitating greater use, and to be able to better track the impact of instrument investment by research facilities and institutions.
Lead(s)	NCRIS facilities
Method	Identifiers for Instruments in Australasia (i4iOz) NCRIS Instruments and Facility PIDs Focus Group RDA Persistent Identifiers for Instruments Working Group Cross NCRIS Microscopy Focus Group
Inputs	Research Data Alliance PIDINST Schema i4iOZ best practices for Instrument Identifiers (v 2.0) i4iOZ best practices for Facility Identifiers PID enabled Infrastructure uplift (repository and data collection) PID Ready Platforms - Vendor Strategy
Outputs	Guidelines for adoption of PIDs for instruments and facilities

2.2.3 PIDs for researchers and contributors

Goal	Increase the adoption of ORCIDs to enable a more complete understanding of the connections between researchers, projects, organisations, research inputs and outputs
Lead(s)	AAF
Method	AAF Australian ORCID Consortium (AOC) AOC Members – Engagement Strategy

2.2.4 PIDs for research data including NTROs

Goal	Increase the adoption of DOIs for research data and related materials including reports, theses, instruments and particularly Non-Traditional Research Outputs (NTROs) such as images, creative works and practitioner-based research
Lead(s)	ARDC
Method	ARDC DataCite DOI Consortium PID Ready Platforms -Vendor Strategy

2.2.5 PIDs for research projects

Goal	Increase the adoption of RAiDs (as the ISO standard for research projects) to enable a more complete understanding of research projects, supporting impact tracking and transparency
Lead(s)	ARDC
Method	ARDC RAiD service PID Ready Platforms -Vendor Strategy

2.2.6 PIDs for research institutions and organisations

Goal	Support National PID Strategy and Funder Action Plans and policy in their
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	aspirations to identify and connect research institutions and organisations using ROR
Lead(s)	ARDC
Method	PID Ready Platforms -Vendor Strategy NCRIS infrastructure uplift

2.2.7 PIDs for physical samples

Goal	Increase the visibility and uptake of IGSNs as the preferred PID for physical samples.
Lead(s)	ARDC
Method	ARDC IGSN service (part of DataCite DOI Consortium) ARDC’s membership of IGSN eV PID Ready Platforms -Vendor Strategy

3. Underpinning service delivery

Engagement and awareness raising with stakeholders is vital to the success of the national strategy. The ARDC and AAF each operate PID services that underpin the National PID Strategy and collaborate to provide a joint Secretariat to support the National PID Strategic Advisory Group's work.

3.1 ARDC PID Services and Leadership

ARDC is Australia’s leading data infrastructure facility. ARDC’s vision is to provide Australian researchers with competitive advantage through data and its strategy is to deliver large thematic research data commons programs in key disciplines including health, environment, HASS and indigenous. As a government funded NCRIS facility, ARDC works to provide the leadership, technology, guidance and PID infrastructure services that are the basis of enabling the nationwide adoption of priority PIDs, which are key to realisation of sector aspirations set out in the National PID Strategy. The ARDC applies co-design principles to collectively identify, advance and realise shared goals and the shared vision of the National PID Strategy.

ARDC’s PID services

- ARDC DataCite DOI Consortium (DOIs, IGSNs)
- Global Registration Authority for the RAiD ISO standard (RAiDs)

- Handle Service

ARDC is also leading and/or participating in a wide range of PID initiatives internationally (see section 1.2 International Alignment). Advice and the development of guiding materials for PID implementation and use (such as best practices for instrument and facility PIDs; National PID Benchmarking materials) are also within ARDC's remit. ARDC develops and operates discovery products that are built on underlying databases which are heavily PID enabled, including Research Link Australia and Research Data Australia. In 2026, to better meet stakeholders needs, ARDC may explore further development such as: a unified national 'PID graph' (a single database drawing on PIDs and their inter-connectedness), with stakeholder dashboard views. This is an example of how PIDs can be used at national scale to power research discovery and insights through products that are fit for purpose.

3.2 AAF PID services

The AAF operates Australia's identity federation. AAF's goal is to transform Australia's research, teaching, and learning communities by delivering innovative solutions that provide secure access to high value digital resources and infrastructure. The AAF leads the Australian ORCID Consortium, providing local support, assisting with member integrations and encouraging national uptake of ORCID in organisations. The Australian ORCID Consortium helps members understand the benefits and how they can get the most value from their membership. As Consortium Lead, the AAF is proud to provide a national service to support ORCID adoption at member institutions.